

IMIDOCHLORIDES. PART X. CONDENSATION OF BENZANILIDE IMIDOCHLORIDE WITH PHENOLS : A NEW SYNTHESIS OF HYDROXYBENZOPHENONES

BY (MISS) RAGINI PHADKE AND R. C. SHAH

Shah, Chaubal and Ichaporia (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 650; 1935, 894) achieved a new synthesis of *p*-dialkylaminobenzophenones through the condensation of benzanilide imidochloride with dialkyl anilines in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. It is now found that hydroxybenzophenones can be conveniently synthesised through the condensation of benzanilide imidochloride with phenols. The new method in which the hydroxybenzophenones are obtained in satisfactory yields appears to be of general applicability. The work also supports the mechanism of Hoesch reaction as put forward by Stephen (*ibid.*, 1920, 117, 1529).

Shah, Chaubal and Ichaporia (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 650; 1935, 894) achieved a new synthesis of *p*-dialkylaminobenzophenones through the condensation of benzanilide imidochloride with dialkylanilines in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride.

It has now been found that benzanilide imidochloride undergoes similar nuclear condensation with phenols. Thus, benzanilide imidochloride (I) has been condensed with resorcinol, resorcinol dimethyl ether, orcinol, catechol, hydroquinone, phloroglucinol, pyrogallol, phenol, anisole, α - and β naphthols, and resacetophenone, in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride in dry ether, dry nitrobenzene or without any solvent.

Resorcinol, when condensed with benzanilide imidochloride (I), gave 2:4-dihydroxy-(phenylimino)benzophenone (II), identical with the product obtained by the condensation of 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone (III) and aniline. The anil (II) easily hydrolysed to give 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone (III). Previously Stephen (*ibid.*, 1920, 117, 1529) had directly condensed benzanilide imidochloride with resorcinol without any condensing agent, and obtained minute quantities of a product, which he considered to be the keto-anil (II), as on hydrolysis it gave 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone (III).

Orcinol, phloroglucinol and α - and β -naphthols on similar condensations gave the corresponding *keto-anils*, and the latter hydrolysed to the corresponding known ketones, namely, 2:4-dihydroxy-6-methyl- and 2:4:6-trihydroxy-benzophenones and 1-hydroxy-4-benzoyl- and 2-hydroxy-1-benzoyl-naphthalenes respectively.

The anils, which are new compounds, are coloured substances, and some are unexpectedly highly stable to acids. The hydrolysis of the anil, in general, could

case and the isolation of keto-anils of type (II), which have structural similarity to the ketimide (V), supposed to be formed during the Hoesch reaction, strongly supports the above view of the mechanism of the Hoesch reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation of Benzanilide Imidochloride with Resorcinol: 2:4-Dihydroxybenzophenone

2:4-Dihydroxy(phenylimino)benzophenone.—To a mixture of dry resorcinol (3.5 g., 1 mol.) and benzanilide imidochloride (7.0 g., 1 mol.) in dry ether, protected from moisture, an ethereal suspension of anhydrous aluminium chloride (6.3 g., 1.5 mols.) was added drop by drop. There was a simultaneous evolution of heat and fumes of hydrogen chloride. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for half an hour, the ether evaporated and the orange colored oil poured in ice-cold hydrochloric acid. The yellow granular solid (8.5 g.), thus obtained, was the *keto-anil* and after washing with a dilute solution of sodium bicarbonate was crystallised from hot benzene in lemon-yellow needles, m.p. 235°. (Found: N, 4.9. $C_{15}H_{16}O_2N$ requires N, 4.8 per cent). Stephen (*loc. cit.*) gives m.p. 228-30°. It is soluble in alcohol, acetic acid, benzene and alkali. Its alcoholic solution gives a brown coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

Diacetyl derivative (acetic anhydride and pyridine) was crystallised from alcohol in white silky needles, m.p. 126-27°. (Found: C, 74.5; H, 5.4. $C_{22}H_{18}O_4N$ requires C, 74.0; H, 5.1 per cent).

Dibenzoyl derivative (benzoyl chloride and pyridine) was crystallised from dilute alcohol in white needles, m.p. 163°. (Found: C, 77.4; H, 5.1. $C_{22}H_{22}O_4N.H_2O$ requires C, 77.0; H, 4.8 per cent).

Dimethyl ether (methyl iodide, potassium carbonate and acetone) was crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 134-35°. (Found: C, 79.2; H, 5.8. $C_{21}H_{18}O_2N$ requires C, 79.4; H, 6.0 per cent).

Hydrolysis of the Anil.—The anil (12.5 g.), dissolved in alcohol, was refluxed with hydrochloric acid (30 c.c.) for 3 hours. The alcohol was distilled off and the solution diluted to give a buff product (8.3 g.) which was crystallised from hot water in white needles, m. p. and mixed m. p. with an authentic sample of 2: 4-dihydroxybenzophenone, 143-44°.

2: 4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone was crystallised from alcohol in red micro-crystals, m.p. 297°. (Found: N, 13.9. $C_{15}H_{14}O_6N_4$ requires N, 14.2 per cent).

Condensation of 2: 4-Dihydroxybenzophenone with Aniline.—2: 4-Dihydroxybenzophenone (1 g.), freshly distilled aniline (1 g.) and powdered zinc chloride (0.7 g.), protected from moisture, were heated together in an oil-bath at 200° for half an hour. The oily mass was poured in ice-water and the solid, thus obtained, washed successively with dilute hydrochloric acid and hot water to remove unreacted aniline and ketone. It crystallised from hot benzene in lemon-yellow needles, m.p. 235°. Mixed melting point with the *keto-anil* obtained above was undepressed.

Condensation of Benzanilide Imidochloride with Resorcinol Dimethyl Ether

2:4-Dimethoxybenzophenone.—Resorcinol dimethyl ether (4.2 g., 1 mol.) and benzanilide imidochloride (6.4 g., 1 mol.) were condensed in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.5 g., 1.5 mols.) in dry ether as above. On working up the reaction mixture similarly, a yellow oil was obtained. This was extracted with ether and the extract on slow evaporation gave colorless needles (2.5 g.). On recrystallisation from dilute alcohol colorless needles of 2:4-dimethoxybenzophenone, m. p. and mixed m. p. with an authentic specimen, 83-85°, were obtained (König and Kostanecki, *Ber.*, 1906, 39, 4028, give m.p. 87-88°; Kauffmann and Panwitz, *ibid.*, 1910, 43, 1207, give m.p. 83°).

Attempts were made to isolate the keto-anil formed during the reaction by carrying out the condensation at 0°, but only the ketone was obtained.

Condensation of Benzanilide Imidochloride with Catechol

3:4-Dihydroxybenzophenone.—Catechol (4 g.), benzanilide imidochloride (8 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (7.5 g.) were refluxed in dry ether for 4 hours. On working up the reaction mixture a red oil was obtained from which the keto-anil could not be isolated in a pure state and hence it was directly hydrolysed by refluxing with alcoholic hydrochloric acid for 6 hours. On dilution, and keeping overnight at room temperature a white solid (2.4 g.) separated. It was crystallised from hot water in colorless prisms, m.p. 134°. (Rosenmund and Lohfert, *Ber.*, 1928, 61B, 2601, give m.p. 134°).

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone was crystallised from acetic acid in red micro-needles, m.p. 282° (decomp.). (Found: N, 14.3. $C_{12}H_{14}O_6N_4$ requires N, 14.2 per cent).

*Condensation of Benzanilide Imidochloride with Orcinol:**2:4-Dihydroxy-6-methylbenzophenone*

2:4-Dihydroxy-6-methyl(phenylimino)benzophenone.—Anhydrous orcinol (3 g.) and benzanilide imidochloride (6 g.) were condensed in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.2 g.) in dry ether as usual. The orange solid obtained on working up the reaction mixture was the hydrochloride of the keto-anil. As it could not be crystallised, it was directly hydrolysed to the anil by treating its alcoholic solution with sodium bicarbonate. On dilution the anil separated as a sticky cream-coloured solid and was crystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum in colorless rhomboid needles, m.p. 102-104° (decomp.). (Found: N, 4.3. $C_{20}H_{17}O_2N$ requires N, 4.6 per cent). Its alcoholic solution gave a faint orange coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The hydrochloride was prepared by passing gaseous hydrogen chloride into an ethereal solution of the anil, m.p. 264°. (Found: N, 3.8; Cl, 10.5. $C_{20}H_{16}O_2NCl$ requires N, 4.1; Cl, 10.3 per cent).

Hydrolysis of the Anil.—The anil (5 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing with alcoholic hydrochloric acid when on working up as usual, 2:4-dihydroxy-6-methylbenzophenone

was obtained. It was crystallised from hot water in colorless needles (1 g.), m.p. 141°. Hoesch (*Ber.*, 1915, 48, 1130) gives the same m.p. Its alcoholic solution gave a brown-red coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

2: 4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone separated as red micro-crystals, m.p. 226°. (Found: N, 14.0. $C_{20}H_{16}O_6N_4$ requires N, 13.7 per cent).

Condensation of Benzanilide Imidochloride with Resacetophenone

2-Benzoyl-4-acetylresorcinol.—To a mixture of resacetophenone (4 g.) and benzanilide imidochloride (6.2 g.), anhydrous aluminium chloride (6 g.), dissolved in dry nitrobenzene, was added gradually. After keeping at room temperature for half an hour the contents, protected from moisture, were heated for 6 hours at 95-100° when hydrogen chloride was evolved. The dark oil was poured in ice-cold hydrochloric acid. After removal of the nitrobenzene by steam-distillation, the residue in the flask was dissolved in sodium hydroxide (10%, 150 c.c.) and filtered to remove the insoluble benzanilide (3.3 g.). The filtrate on acidification gave a chocolate coloured product (1.6 g.) which was washed with hot water to remove the unreacted resacetophenone. It was extracted with petroleum ether and the residue crystallised repeatedly from 50% alcohol (charcoal) in colorless needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 2-benzoyl-4-acetylresorcinol, 167-68°. (Found: C, 70.0; H, 4.9. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{14}O_2$: C, 70.1; H, 4.7 per cent). (Desai and Vakil. *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1940 12A, 394, give m.p. 165°). Its alcoholic solution gave a deep red coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

Condensation of Benzanilide Imidochloride with Phloroglucinol :

2:4:6-Trihydroxybenzophenone

2:4:6-Trihydroxy(phenylimino)benzophenone.—Anhydrous phloroglucinol (4 g.) was condensed with benzanilide imidochloride (7.2 g.) in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (6.4 g.) in dry ether, as usual. The yellow anil (8 g.) obtained was washed with a sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 191° (decomp.). (Found: N, 4.7. $C_{18}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 4.5 per cent). Its alcoholic solution gave no coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

Triacetyl derivative (acetic anhydride and concentrated sulphuric acid) was crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 115-16°. (Found: C, 69.7; H, 5.0. $C_{25}H_{21}O_6N$ requires C, 69.6; H, 4.9 per cent).

Tribenzoyl derivative (benzoyl chloride and pyridine) was crystallised from benzene after adding petroleum ether in yellow needles, m.p. 182°. (Found: C, 77.8; H, 4.8. $C_{40}H_{27}O_3N$ requires C, 77.8; H, 4.4 per cent).

Trimethyl ether (dimethyl sulphate, potassium carbonate and acetone) was crystallised from alcohol (50%) in colorless, glistening plates, m.p. 148-50°. (Found: C, 76.4; H, 5.2. $C_{22}H_{21}O_3N$ requires C, 76.1; H, 5.4 per cent).

Hydrolysis of the Anil.—The anil (6 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing with alcoholic hydrochloric acid for 4 hours. The oil obtained was extracted with ether, ether eva-

porated and the product crystallised from hot water in yellow silky needles (1.8 g.), m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of 2:4:6-trihydroxybenzophenone, 165° (Hoesch, *Ber.*, 1915, 48, 1130, give the same m.p.).

Condensation of Benzanilide Imidochloride with Pyrogallol

2:3:4-Trihydroxybenzophenone.—Pyrogallol (4 g.) was condensed with benzanilide imidochloride (6.1 g.) in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.6 g.) by refluxing in dry ether for 4 hours. The crude anil obtained, as an oil after working up the reaction mixture as usual, could not be isolated in a pure state and was directly hydrolysed to the ketone (2.3 g.) with alcoholic hydrochloric acid. 2:3:4-Trihydroxybenzophenone obtained was crystallised from hot water in colorless needles, m.p. 140-41° (Fischer and Rapaport, *Ber.*, 1913, 46, 2393 give the same m.p.). Its alcoholic solution gave a dark coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The condensation was also carried out on a steam-bath (2 hours) with nitrobenzene as a solvent. The yield, however, was reduced and the product was accompanied with some tarry material.

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone was crystallised from acetic acid in small shining orange needles, m.p. 237° (decomp.). (Found: N, 13.6. $C_{11}H_{14}O_7N_4$ requires N, 13.7 per cent).

Condensation of Benzanilide Imidochloride with Phenol

p-Hydroxybenzophenone.—To a mixture of phenol (2.5 g.) and benzanilide imidochloride (4.6 g.) powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (4.5 g.) was added. After the initial reaction, the mixture, protected from moisture, was heated for 12 hours at 120°-130° during which fumes of hydrogen chloride were evolved. The orange solid was crushed and added to ice-cold hydrochloric acid. The yellow solid obtained was directly crystallised from dilute acetic acid in colorless needles (1.1 g.), m.p. 134-35° (Doebner and Stackmann, *Ber.*, 1877, 10, 1969, give m.p. 134°).

When this condensation was carried out under the usual conditions using ether as a solvent, quantitative yield of phenyl benzoate was obtained; while in nitrobenzene at 160° (6 hours) a tarry mass resulted from which nothing could be isolated.

Acetyl derivative was crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless silky needles, m.p. 82°. Doebner and Stackmann (*loc. cit.*) give m.p. 81°.

Condensation of Benzanilide Imidochloride with Anisole: p-Hydroxybenzophenone.—A mixture of anisole (2.5 g.), benzanilide imidochloride (5.2 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (5 g.) was heated for 5 hours at 130°-140°. The solid obtained on addition to ice-cold hydrochloric acid was refluxed with alcoholic sodium hydroxide (10%) for 6 hours. The alcohol was distilled off and the solution acidified to give a white pasty product. It was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in colorless needles (2 g.), m.p. 134°. Mixed m.p. with a sample of *p*-hydroxybenzophenone obtained above was undepressed.

Low yields were obtained when the condensation was carried out in boiling ether (4 hours); while in nitrobenzene at 130° (4 hours) a pasty product was obtained which could not be crystallised.

Condensation of Benzanilide Imidochloride with α -Naphthol :
1-Hydroxy-4-benzoylnaphthalene

1-Hydroxy-4-(phenylimino)benzoylnaphthalene.— α -Naphthol (4.4 g.) was condensed with benzanilide imidochloride (6.6 g.) in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (6.0 g.) in dry ether as usual. The orange solid obtained on working up the reaction mixture was the anil hydrochloride (10.9 g.). It was hydrolysed with sodium bicarbonate and the anil crystallised from toluene in chocolate coloured granules, m.p. 172-74°. (Found : N, 4.1. $C_{22}H_{17}ON$ requires N, 4.3 per cent). The anil is soluble in alcohol, acetic acid, alkali, benzene and toluene. Its alcoholic solution gave no coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The hydrochloride separated as orange micro-crystals, m.p. 265-68°. (Found : Cl, 10.6. $C_{22}H_{11}ONCl$ requires Cl, 10.3 per cent).

Acetyl derivative was crystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether in buff coloured needles, m.p. 154°. (Found : N, 3.8. $C_{22}H_{19}O_2N$ requires N, 3.8 per cent).

Benzoyl derivative was crystallised from benzene after adding petroleum ether, in colorless needles, m.p. 181°. (Found : N, 3.4. $C_{20}H_{21}O_2N$ requires N, 3.3 per cent).

Hydrolysis of the Anil.—The hydrolysis of the anil could not be carried out under the usual conditions. Even with concentrated potassium hydroxide solution (50%) in a sealed tube at 180°-200° for 8 hours the original compound was recovered ; and with acetic acid and concentrated hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube at 150° for 10 hours only traces of the ketone (m.p. 158-60°) were obtained. Hence the following method was followed for hydrolysis.

The anil (2.4 g.) was dissolved in a minimum quantity of acetic acid and heated with sulphuric acid (40%, 6.2 c.c.) at 130° for 3 hours. On dilution, the ketone separated and it was crystallised from alcohol in golden yellow needles, m.p. 164-65°, yield 0.52 g. Scholl and Seer (*Annalen*, 1912, 394, 151) give the same m.p.

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from alcohol as red micro-needles, m.p. 285° (decomp.). (Found : N, 12.5. $C_{22}H_{16}O_6N_4$ requires N, 12.5 per cent.).

Condensation of Benzanilide Imidochloride with β -Naphthol :
2-Hydroxy-1-benzoylnaphthalene

2-Hydroxy-1-(phenylimino)benzoylnaphthalene.— β -Naphthol (2.4 g.) was condensed with benzanilide imidochloride (6.3 g.) in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.9 g.) in dry ether as usual. The orange anil hydrochloride obtained on working up the reaction mixture was converted into the free anil as above. The anil was crystallised from 50% alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 178°-79°. (Found : N, 4.6. $C_{22}H_{17}ON$ requires N, 4.3 per cent). It is soluble in alcohol, acetic acid, alkali, benzene and acetone but sparingly soluble in ether. Its alcoholic solution gave a feeble orange coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The hydrochloride separated as orange shining plates, m.p. 270°. (Found : N, 3.9 ; Cl, 10.1. $C_{22}H_{16}ONCl$ requires N, 3.9 ; Cl, 10.3 per cent).

Acetyl derivative crystallised from alcohol in tiny, pale yellow needles, m. p. 137-38°. (Found : N, 4.5. $C_{22}H_{10}O_2N$ requires N, 4.1 per cent).

Benzoyl derivative was crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether in yellow needles, m.p. 146-47°. (Found : N, 3.7. $C_{20}H_{12}O_2N$ requires N, 3.3 per cent).

Hydrolysis of the Anil.—Attempts to hydrolyse the anil with alcoholic potassium hydroxide or hydrochloric acid, potassium hydroxide in glycerine, or with concentrated sulphuric acid were unsuccessful, and hence the following method was adopted.

The anil (4 g.) was heated with aqueous potassium hydroxide (50%, 20 c.c.) in a sealed tube at 130°-135° for 5 hours. The solution was then diluted and acidified when a golden yellow solid (2.2 g.) separated. This was repeatedly crystallised from dilute alcohol (25%) when 2-hydroxy-1-benzoylnaphthalene was obtained in pale yellow needles, m.p. 140-41°. Perrier (*Compt. rend.*, 1893, 116, 1141) gives m.p. 141°.

Attempted Condensation of Benzanilide Imidochloride with Hydroquinone

Hydroquinone (4.6 g.) and benzanilide imidochloride (9.2 g.) in ethereal solution were mixed with an ethereal solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (15.7 g., 2.2 moles) and worked up as usual. On crystallisation the product was found to be quinol monobenzoate, m.p. 161-62° (9.7 g.). Will and Johnson (*Ber.*, 1893, 20, 1909) give m.p. 162-63°. With benzoyl chloride and pyridine it gave hydroquinone dibenzoate, m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen, 200-201°. Doebner (*Annalen*, 1881, 210, 263) gives m.p. 199°.

Attempts at this condensation using nitrobenzene as a solvent or without a solvent also resulted in the formation of hydroquinone monobenzoate.

Thanks of the authors are due to (Miss) M.B. Vadh for carrying out some preliminary investigations on the condensation with resorcinol and to (late) Mr. M. Laiwala for the investigation on the condensation with phenol.

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
ROYAL INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BOMBAY.

Received February 15, 1953.